

Metal Complexes of Thiopolycarboxylic Acid Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Cr(III) Complexes with 3,3'-Thiodipropionic Acid

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3, 3'-Thiodipropionic acid forms 1 : 1 coloured complexes with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Cr(III) $[M_2L_2]$ and their structures have been characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, magnetic measurements, Infrared and electronic spectral studies. It was found that all these complexes are high spin octahedral. Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) complexes show normal magnetic moments but copper(II) and Cr(III) show anomalous magnetic behaviour.

METAL complexes of thiopolycarboxylic acids have been the subject of many recent studies¹⁻⁵.

Suzuki et. al.⁶ determined the stability constants of some metal chelates with 3, 3'-thiodipropionic acid and reported 1:1 complexes with six membered ring. 3, 3'-Thiodipropionic acid has two carboxylic groups, and one sulphur atom as donors and hence capable to afford the examples of homonuclear metal-metal interaction⁷. The present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of metal complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II) and Chromium(III) with 3, 3'-thiodipropionic acid $[S(CH_2, CH_2, COOH)_2]$.

Experimental

3,3'-Thiodipropionic acid (Evans Chemetics, Inc., New York) of 98.8% was used as such without further purification. All other chemicals used were of A. R. grade.

Preparation of Complexes : The metal complexes of Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Cr(III) with 3, 3'-thiodipropionic acid were prepared by the general method described here. A solution of hydrated metal chloride (75 ml, 0.2 M) was added to an equimolar solution (75 ml and 115 ml in case of Cr(III) complex) in distilled alcohol. A few drops of concentrated NaOH were added and resulting mixture was refluxed for four hours, over steam bath. In case of Cu(II) and Cr(III), a sky blue and bluish green complexes were obtained respectively but in case of Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II), the resulting mixture was concentrated to 50 ml which yield light pinkish and light greenish complexes respectively on refrigeration for two days. The complexes so formed were filtered, washed with alcohol, acetone and ether and dried in vacuo over calcium chloride.

Physical Measurements : The instruments and methods have been given previously⁴.

Results and Discussion

3, 3'-Thiodipropionic acid forms 1 : 1 coloured

complexes with Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) which are slightly soluble in water and common organic solvents. However Cr(III) complex is almost insoluble in H₂O and common organic solvents. The decomposition temperatures which range between 150-200° show that complexes are thermally quite stable. The molar conductance in D.M.S.O. indicates non-electrolytic nature of these complexes (2.06-3.10 ohm⁻¹ cm⁻² mole⁻¹).

Cobalt(II) Thiodipropionate : The observed magnetic moment 4.92 B.M. of Co(II) thiodipropionate is within the usual range of reported data for high spin octahedral complexes⁸ and suggests octahedral symmetry. The diffuse reflectance spectrum shows three absorption bands at 7.52, 16.25 and 19.60 kK which are similar to the transitions of octahedral symmetry in Cobalt(II) complexes and further supports octahedral symmetry. The observed ν_2 transition at 16.25 kK which is approximately twice but not greater than 2.2 times to that of ν_1 transition (7.52 kK) also indicates that the complex is regular octahedral ($\nu_2/\nu_1 = 2.16$)⁹. Thus magnetic and spectral data suggest octahedral symmetry of the complex. Since ligand has only five donor atoms, the sixth coordination site should be completed by sharing a non-bonded oxygen atom with neighbouring molecule forming a dimer as suggested from molecular weight determination (experimental M=465). A value of β , 0.901 suggests low degree of covalency.

Nickel(II) Thiodipropionate-Monohydrate : It shows magnetic moment 3.27 B.M. and suggests high spin octahedral symmetry. The octahedral stereochemistry is further supported by diffuse reflectance spectrum which shows three bands at 7.50, 14.25 and 23.92 kK. The observed separation of ν_2 and ν_1 transition, 9.67 kK being considerably lower than the calculated value of 11.28 kK for regular octahedral symmetry¹⁰, suggests that the complex is distorted octahedral. This is further supported by ν_2/ν_1 ratio 1.90. The 7.1% decrease in weight at 134° in T.G.A of Nickel complex indicates coordination through a molecule of water. A value at β , 0.935 indicates low degree of covalency.

TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS, MAGNETIC MOMENTS AND DIFFUSE REFLECTANCE SPECTRAL DATA

Complex	C%		H%		S%		Metal %		Magnetic moment	Transition bands in reflectance spectrum
	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.	Found		
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2]_2$	30.61	30.56	3.42	3.44	13.60	13.58	25.04	25.10	4.92	7.52, 16.25, 19.60 kK
$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	28.49	28.50	3.98	4.00	12.67	12.64	23.21	23.24	3.27	7.50, 14.25, 23.92 kK
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2]$	30.02	30.14	3.37	3.36	13.34	13.32	26.40	26.42	1.31	14.70, 26.31 kK
$[\text{Cr}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_4]$	34.17	34.20	3.78	3.84	15.18	15.16	16.45	16.50	3.26	17.46, 24.52 kK

TABLE 2—INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS OF 3,3'-THIODIPROPIONIC ACID AND ITS COMPLEXES*

Complex	$\nu(\text{OH})$ of H_2O	$\nu(\text{OH})$ of COOH	$\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$	$\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{COO})$	$\nu(\text{C-S})$
$\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4\text{S}$	—	3100, S. Br.	1710 (S)	1430 (S)	730 (m)
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2]$	—	—	1585 (S)	1405 (S)	720 (m)
$[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	3370	—	1580 (S)	1415 (S)	705 (m)
$[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_2]$	—	—	1600 (S)	1410 (S)	700 (m)
$[\text{Cr}_2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_4\text{S})_4]$	—	—	1620 (S)	1400 (S)	725 (m)

* All data are in cm^{-1} , S=Sharp, m=medium, br=broad.

Cu(II) Thiodipropionate : The observed magnetic moment value 1.31 B.M. is subnormal in case of Cu(II)-thiodipropionate and suggests spin-spin coupling between unpaired electrons of neighbouring copper atoms. The diffuse reflectance spectrum shows two transition bands at 14.70 kK and 26.31 kK indicating octahedral symmetry¹¹ and dimeric nature of the complex.¹² The copper(II) complex will be distorted octahedral due to John Teller effect. Thus in copper(II) octahedral complex, metal ion is penta-coordinated by the ligand and the remaining sixth coordination position will be occupied by Cu—Cu bond forming a dimer. This is supported by magnetic, I.R., diffuse reflectance spectral data and molecular weight determination which comes out to be 468.

Cr(III) Thiodipropionate : The observed magnetic moment value 3.26 B.M. is considerably lower than the spin only value as well as reported data for octahedral complexes and suggests inter or intra molecular antiferromagnetism between Cr(III) ions. The diffuse reflectance spectrum shows two strong bands at 17.46 and 24.52 kK, suggesting octahedral symmetry. Thus Cr(III) complex is high spin octahedral in which metal-metal interaction between chromium ions form a polymeric structure.

I.R. Spectra : Infrared spectrum of 3,3'-thiodipropionic acid and its complexes were recorded in the region of $4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Disappearance of $\nu(\text{OH})$ vibrations and shift in $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{COO})$ vibrations^{13,14} towards lower wave number in complexes indicate coordination through both bonded and non-bonded oxygen atoms of the carboxylic groups. The C—S stretching frequency shifted towards lower wave number in complexes with respect to free ligand, indicating coordination through sulphur. Thus ligand acts as pentadentate in all the metal complexes forming a six numbered ring with the metal ion, as the non-bonded oxygen atoms are supplied from neighbouring molecule.

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